

A STUDY ABOUT THE MECHANISM OF ULTRASONIC LIQUID INFILTRATION FOR SiC_r/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

By analyzing the ultrasonic cavitation in several kinds of transparent liquid medium, we have investigated the cavitation effect in liquid. It is considered that the shock wave created by the cavitation in aluminium melt will induce a higher pressure and an elevated temperature field around the fibers, which can promote the wetting between fiber and aluminium and have aluminium melt infiltrate into the fibers. Moreover, the experiment result shows that the fiber resonance matching with the cavitation is also an important factor for SiC_r/Al composites preparing. There exists a damage of the ultrasonic vibration on SiC fiber.

Keywords: ultrasonic infiltration, silicon carbide fiber and aluminium

1. INTRODUCTION

A new technique fabricating SiC_r/Al composites, called ultrasonic liquid infiltration method, was developed successfully in 1985^[1,2]. By unceasing improvement in experiment apparatus and processing parameters, now we have fabricated SiC yarn fiber reinforced aluminium composite wire(preform wire) with a continuous length longer than 500 meters and an ultimate tensile strength higher than 1500MPa^[3]. As the application of this technique, we have developed the processing to fabricate SiC_r/Al composite tape, CF/Al composite wire, SiC_{CVD}/Al composite wire and the woven fiber cloth reinforced aluminium plate and so on. Recently, some patents and research work about ultrasonic technique in fabrication of composite materials are presented, which contain ones to prepare hybrid fiber^[4], to fabricate continuous fiber reinforced aluminium^[5], and also to introduce whisker or particulate directly into molten aluminium^[6~8]. It has been demonstrated that ultrasonic technique is an effective approach for

improving the wettability and compatibility between the reinforcement and aluminium and then having them to be composites. Because ultrasonic technique applications in fabrication of metal matrix composites only began some years ago, there exists several problems for this new method, especially it is not clear what mechanism promotes fiber wetting with aluminium melt. In the present work, we are about to infer the presentation of cavitation in aluminium melt by observing the physical phenomenon in several transparent liquid medium during ultrasonic vibration being introduced into them. We will confirm that there are other factors to influence ultrasonic infiltration of SiC_f/Al composites.

2. ULTRASONIC CAVITATION IN LIQUID

2.1. Cavitation Effect

It is common known that we can divide ultrasound into two sorts, called detective ultrasound and high-intensity ultrasound, respectively. The former is used for gathering messages by means of its penetrability through material such as ultrasonic detection of defects and medical ultrasonic diagnosis, the latter is for treating material by using its high energy such as ultrasonic cleaning, ultrasonic weld and ultrasonic machine etc. High-intensity ultrasound has a general frequency in the range of $10^8 \sim 10^4$ Hz. The ultrasonic generator power used in our MMC preparation is from 500 to 2000 Watts.

When an ultrasonic energy is introduced into a liquid, a temporary negative pressure arises in some liquid regions. An excessive tensile stress induced creates bubbles or voids in the regions. Those bubbles are in unsteady state, oscillate under the action of ultrasonic field. If the negative acoustic pressure exceeds some certain value, the bubbles expand rapidly and subsequently collapse or implode at a fast speed. While the bubbles collapse, a rather substantial compressive shock wave forms and propagates through the liquid. This process is called cavitation effect of high-intensity ultrasound. The bubbles that give rise to cavitation effect are called cavitation nucleus. The cavitation nucleus may be created by the negative acoustic pressure as mentioned above, possibly also from the air bubble dissolved in liquid or from the vapor bubble induced by thermal rising and falling in liquid. It depends upon a series of physical configuration whether the cavitation nucleus collapses or not, which contains ultrasonic power, frequency, liquid temperature, viscosity, density, container shape and so on. If the nucleus is too small, it redissolves in liquid under hydrostatic pressure, oppositely, too large, it floats off liquid.

2.2 Cavitation in Different Liquid Medium

In order to investigate the behavior of molten aluminium melt during ultrasonic energy being introduced into, firstly let us input ultrasound into several transparent medium. In our experiment, we selected fresh tap water, distilled water, castor oil and paraffin wax as the ultrasonic medium. After an ultrasonic

horn was inserted in a beaker containing 500ml liquid medium, we began to adjust the generator frequency and power until the ultrasonic transducer came to be in resonant state. It was readily seen that there was a tail flow below the horn tip and the liquid was full of many moving bubbles. Certainly, some of those bubbles collapsed under acoustic pressure, the others gathered, grew up and floated off of the liquid, or perhaps redissolved in the liquid.

When the ultrasonic horn tip is taken off the water level, if the water stayed on the horn tip atomizes rapidly, it is also demonstrated that the transducer is in resonant state. The physical parameters in the ultrasonic resonant state and the bubble features observed in different medium are summarized in Table 1. The power listed should be the minimum value above which the transducer could be resonated. The generator frequency only had a little difference for the several medium, but it is certain to influence cavitation effect. The ultrasonic field theory states

Table 1. The physical parameters and the bubble features under the resonant state

Medium	Temp. (°C)	Power (W)	Frequency (kHz)	Bubble amount	Bubble shape
Fresh tap water	15	750	20.1	more	small, round
Distilled water	15	800	49	little	smaller, round
Castor oil	15	700	18.7	little	large, ellipsoid
Paraffin wax	70	500	18.3	less	larger, ellipsoid
Aluminium melt	700	750	19.5	----	----

that the bubble oscillates under the action of ultrasonic field, but may not necessarily collapse and cavitate^[9]. In a certain acoustic power, only when there exists some relationship between the acoustic frequency f and the resonance frequency f_0 of the bubble, the bubble collapses. That is, $f < f_0$, the bubble collapses and cavitation takes place. If $f > f_0$, the bubble oscillations become complex, and collapse does not occur. As an example of water in atmosphere, the resonance frequency f_0 of the bubble with different radius R_0 could be calculated as follows^[10]:

R_0 (mm)	3.3	.33	.033	.003
f_0 (kHz)	1	10	100	1000

That means, the smaller bubble is easy to satisfy the condition $f < f_0$. Consequently, the bubbles with a small radius cavitate easily, large bubbles only appear a complex oscillation and then gather, float off the liquid. We shall have a further research to find the relationship of generator frequency vs ultrasonic

acoustic frequency.

The main effect of cavitation is creating a high pressure when the bubble collapses. For example, a bubble with 0.1 mm diameter collapses only in $5\mu s$, the shock wave creates a thousand atmospheric pressure [10]. Moreover, because of fast molecule motion while cavitation occurring, the liquid temperature in acted region goes up, which is called ultrasonic thermal effect. After introducing ultrasonic vibration in water (600 ml) for 40 minutes, we found that the average temperature was from $10^{\circ}C$ to $47^{\circ}C$. And if in paraffin wax, the temperature of wax melt could remain unchanged due to the ultrasonic thermal effect.

3. ULTRASONIC LIQUID INFILTRATION OF SiC_x/Al COMPOSITES

When we inputted ultrasound into molten aluminium melt (at $700^{\circ}C$) and had the transducer vibrate by adjusting the generator frequency and the power, we found that the physical parameters were in the same range as in the other liquid medium as shown in Table 1. Consequently, the cavitation effect demonstrated to be in water, castor oil or paraffin wax melt should exist in liquid aluminium too. We can have a detail investigation on ultrasonic behaviors in liquid, by substituting low temperature transparent medium (water, oil etc) instead of aluminium melt. In order to fabricate continuous fiber reinforced aluminium composites by ultrasonic liquid infiltration method, we designed an apparatus as shown in Figure 1. The fiber (filament) is pulled continuously through a crucible with aluminium melt.

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of fabricating continuous fiber reinforced aluminium composites, 1. fiber 2. crucible containing aluminium melt 3. ultrasonic horn 4. transducer 5. generator 6. composite wire winding wheel

Ultrasonic energy is inputted into the system via an ultrasonic horn attaching to the transducer. By the action of ultrasound, the fiber that is not wetted by liquid aluminium originally becomes wetted and then aluminium infiltrates into fiber. The fiber pulled out from the crucible becomes a continuous composite wire. Figure 2 shows the metallographic photographs of two kinds of SiC fiber reinforced aluminium composite wire. One used a yarn SiC (Nicalon) fiber, manufactured by Nippon Carbon Co.Ltd, with a diameter of $12\mu m$ and 500 filaments for a yarn. Another was a CVD single SiC (SCS-2) fiber, manufactured by Textron Co.

Ltd, having a diameter of $142\mu\text{m}$. The matrix was an industrial pure aluminium (Al) 99.6 wt%). By using this method, we can also fabricate the other continuous fiber

Figure 2. Metallograph photograph of SiC_f/Al composite wire section
 a. $\text{SiC(Nicalon)}/\text{Al}$ b. $\text{SiC(SCS-2)}/\text{Al}$

reinforced aluminium composites. According to the cavitation effect, we can have a discussion about the ultrasonic infiltration mechanisms. The air brought in aluminium melt by fiber and the gas dissolved in aluminium melt may become the cavitation nuclei. If some of those bubbles collapse, a high pressure will be created around the fiber, which promotes aluminium melt to infiltrate into the fiber. Because the collapse speed is extremely high, fiber and aluminium become composite wire rapidly. In addition, the ultrasonic thermal effect forms a high temperature field near the fiber, which is favourable for improving the wettability between fiber and liquid aluminium. In this fabrication process, the fibers chemical damage is little (generally the strength degradation is less than 5%), owing to the short contacting time between fiber and aluminium melt. There exists a lot of other factors for infiltration of liquid aluminium into fiber, with the exception of ultrasonic cavitation. For instance, we have found that the infiltration speed and composites quality depended on how many fiber numbers containing in a bundle of fiber. After increasing SiC(Nicalon) fiber from one yarn (500 filaments/yarn) to five yarn and ten yarn (5000 filaments), the more the fiber number was, the more difficult the infiltration became. If too many fibers existed, the penetration resistance of liquid aluminium through the fiber bundle decreased and aluminium infiltration needed more time from the outside of fiber bundle to the inner. Sometime we only obtain a semi composite wire which has a composite shell and still contains some original fiber in inner, because of no enough infiltration time. Similarly, if fiber diameter is not the same, the infiltration is different. Comparing the preparation process of $\text{SiC(SCS-2, } \varphi 142\mu\text{m)}$, $\text{SiC(Nicalon, } \varphi 12\mu\text{m)}$ and $\text{C(T300, } \varphi 7\mu\text{m)}$ fiber reinforced aluminium composite wire, the former was found the easiest, the latter the most difficult. Fiber direction also influences the infiltration quality. In an extended fiber bundle, if there was some cross fiber in perpendicular direction, the infiltration became more difficult. When brought a SiC cloth below the ultrasonic horn tip, only if we used a horn with a high energy density, we had aluminium melt into fiber cloth possibly. It is considered that there is a slight vibration of the fiber in ultrasonic field, called fiber resonance, to match the

ultrasonic cavitation. Increasing fiber number or adding cross fiber restricts the fiber vibration and hence is unfavourable for such resonance. By using an ultrasonic horn with a higher energy density, prolonging the period of ultrasonic infiltration on fiber appropriately and adjusting the other processing parameters, we fabricated SiC(Nicalon) fiber cloth reinforced aluminium composites successfully. the thickest one contained a 7-ply yarn fiber, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Metallograph photograph of SiC(Nicalon)/Al composites having a cross yarn fiber.

A further research is how to fabricate composite plate or continuous composite tape having some cross yarn fiber in it. Moreover, if a higher power ultrasonic equipment is applied, it would be possible to realize the infiltration of aluminium into a mechanical component knitting with yarn fiber by ultrasonic liquid infiltrating directly .

4. THE DAMAGE OF ULTRASONIC VIBRATION TO SiC FIBER

The ultrasonic energy is trasmitted to fiber via liquid medium. In this process, we found that there existed fiber damage. Figure 4 shows a SiC yarn fiber fracturing in water. After the ultrasonic transducer was in resonant state, we

Figure 4. SiC(Nicalon) yarn fiber fracture process in water under the action of ultrasound (The cylinder over fiber is a horn tip). a.initial state b. after 1 min. c. after 3 min. d. the whole fiber fractured

could readily see an apparent vibration in the middle of the fiber (Fig.4(a)). We think this slight vibration is favourable to aluminium infiltration. Obviously, increasing fiber number or adding cross fiber restricts the fiber vibration. After vibrated about for one minute, SiC fiber began to break down (Fig.4(b)) , until about five minutes the whole yarn fiber fractured. This experiment indicates that the center of horn tip has the maximum energy, and the fiber's vibration creates a high circle flexural or tensile deformation which fatigues the fiber to fracture.

We also found that the fiber damage needed to spend more time when increasing either fiber bundle number or cross fiber in unidirectional fibers. This demonstrates the opinion mentioned previously that the fiber vibration(resonance) is necessary to match the ultrasonic cavitation, and increasing fiber number or adding cross fiber is unfavourable for ultrasonic infiltration of liquid aluminium into fiber.

In the process preparing SiC_r/Al composite wire, because the fiber vibrating time is too short(less than one second), the fiber damage may be negligible. But a few minutes vibration process should be given a special attention in order to avoid fiber damage.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The main mechanism of ultrasonic liquid infiltration is the cavitation which creates a high pressure and high temperature field around SiC fiber, then pressing aluminium melt into fibers.
- 2) The fiber vibration is favourable for aluminium infiltration. Increasing fiber number or adding cross fiber may restrict such vibration and hence multiplies the difficulty of infiltration.
- 3) There is a mechanical damage of ultrasound on SiC yarn fiber. It becomes possible for the damage to be avoided if the fiber vibration time is less than a few minutes.

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